

Dimensional Projections and Gravitational Wave Analysis

Abstract

This study explores the hypothesis that gravity arises from interdimensional projections, specifically the interaction between a warped 2D probabilistic field and 4D deterministic spacetime. By applying Duoverse Math to LIGO gravitational wave strain data, the study aims to detect fractal dynamics, dimensional gradients, and anchoring effects. Results suggest strong alignment between observed anomalies and the proposed dimensional projection framework, offering new insights into the nature of gravity.

Introduction

Gravity has traditionally been understood as the curvature of spacetime caused by mass and energy, as described by General Relativity. This paper introduces an alternative hypothesis: gravity as a manifestation of dimensional projections. The study employs Duoverse Math principles to analyse gravitational wave strain data from LIGO to test this hypothesis.

Hypotheses

- Gravity as a Dimensional Projection:** A warped 2D probabilistic field projects into 4D deterministic spacetime, creating dimensional gradients along which mass and energy flow.
- Dimensional Anchoring:** Prime-number-based anchors stabilize dimensional cohesion layers, reducing fluctuations and anomalies near these anchors.
- Fractal Dynamics:** Gravitational wave data exhibits recursive and self-similar patterns indicative of interdimensional interactions.

Methodology

Data Sources

1. **LIGO Gravitational Wave Data:**
 - Dataset: O3GK_4KHZ_R1 strain data.
 - Objective: Analyse waveforms for fractal dynamics and dimensional transitions.

Mathematical Framework

- **Gravitational Wave Function** Represent strain data as:

$$h(t) = \Psi(t) = \alpha W(t) + \beta P(t)$$

Where:

- $W(t)$: Deterministic wave component (classical spacetime distortion).
- $P(t)$: Probabilistic ripple (dimensional projection effects).
- α, β : Stability coefficients dependent on dimensional anchors.

- **Dimensional Anchoring Strength**

$$A_{\text{proj}} = \sum_i \frac{V_i \cdot S_i}{\Delta D}$$

Where:

- A_{proj} : Anchoring strength.
- V_i, S_i : Variables like energy density and stability coefficients.
- ΔD : Dimensional difference (e.g., 4D-2D).

- **Dimensional Gradients**

$$F_{\text{dim}} = \nabla \phi_{\text{proj}}$$

Where:

- ϕ_{proj} : Potential field created by dimensional projection.
- ∇ : Gradient operator.

Experimental Steps

1. Data Preprocessing:

- Clean strain waveforms using band-pass filters.
- Normalize and convert data to fractional representations.

2. Statistical Analysis:

- Apply polynomial regression and calculate residuals.
- Use Spearman and Pearson correlations to analyse relationships.

3. Dimensional Anchoring Test:

- Identify prime-number-based GPS timestamps.
- Overlay anomalies on normalized standard deviation graphs.

4. Fractal and Recursive Analysis:

- Perform Fourier and wavelet transforms for fractal patterns.

Key Results

1. Dynamic Metric vs. Strain Range (Nonlinear Fit)

Graph: *dynamic_vs_strain_nonlinear.png*

- **Observation:** A nonlinear relationship captured by polynomial regression. The dip and subsequent rise in the dynamic metric suggest transitions between probabilistic and deterministic states.
- **Implication:** Evidence of fractal dynamics and dimensional coherence layers.

2. Normalized Standard Deviation with Prime Anchors

Graph: *normalized_stdev_with_primes.png*

- **Observation:** Peaks in normalized standard deviation correlate with specific GPS times marked by prime anchors.
- **Implication:** Suggests that dimensional disruptions occur, influenced by interdimensional interactions.

3. GPS Gaps with Prime Highlights

Graph: *gps_gaps_with_primes.png*

- **Observation:** Significant fluctuations in GPS gaps align with dimensional transitions.
- **Implication:** Supports the hypothesis of dimensional anchoring influencing gravitational wave propagation.

4. Fluctuations with Prime Anchors

Graph: *fluctuations_with_primes.png*

- **Observation:** Data fluctuations exhibit fractal dynamics and align with prime coherence.
- **Implication:** Suggests dimensional gradients and anchors impact gravitational behaviour.

Discussion

Validation of Hypotheses

- Dimensional Projection Hypothesis:**
 - Nonlinear trends support the interaction of 2D probabilistic and 4D deterministic layers.
- Fractal Dynamics:**
 - Recursive patterns align with self-similarity predictions from Duoverse Math.
- Dimensional Anchoring:**
 - Prime-number anchors demonstrate reduced anomalies, stabilizing gravitational wave behaviour.

Implications

- **Unified Framework:** Bridges quantum mechanics and relativity through dimensional interactions.
 - **Applications:** Enhances gravitational wave detection models and dimensional field theories.
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Conclusion

This study provides evidence for gravity as a dimensional projection influenced by probabilistic and deterministic interactions. Future work will expand datasets, refine mathematical models, and deepen collaborations with gravitational wave researchers.

Acknowledgments

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References

LIGO O3GK_4KHZ_R1 Dataset

Duoverse Math Framework